

EVALUATION OF DRINKING WATER QUALITY BASED ON PHYSICOCHEMICAL AND MICROBIAL PARAMETERS IN COMMUNITY SOURCES OF PITHORAGARH, UTTARAKHAND

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ABSTRACT

Water is a vital resource for all forms of life, offering essential health benefits and supporting the survival and well-being of living organisms. Ensuring access to clean and safe drinking water is crucial, particularly in remote and ecologically sensitive regions. This study focuses on the physicochemical assessment of community water sources in the Himalayan region of Pithoragarh, Uttarakhand, India. The primary objective was to evaluate the seasonal variations in water quality through monthly analysis of various physicochemical parameters over one year. Water samples were collected from multiple community sources and tested for pH (6.0-7.9), water temperature (7-21°C), air temperature (10-22°C), total dissolved solids 332-498 mg/L, dissolved oxygen 5.2-7.9 mg/L, carbon dioxide 0.4-2.6 mg/L, alkalinity 59-287 mg/L, biological oxygen demand 0.8-3.1 mg/L, and electrical conductivity 308-799 $\mu\text{S/cm}$. After that, find out the statistically significant differences between the various parameters, as shown by p-values less than 0.05. These parameters showed noticeable fluctuations throughout the year, indicating the influence of seasonal and environmental factors on water quality. In addition to chemical analysis, microbiological examination revealed the presence of bacteria in several water sources, such as *E. coli*, *Salmonella*, *Shigella*, *Clostridium* & *Campylobacter*. After that, we observed the different bacterial characteristics, such as colour, shape, and surface. The presence of bacteria raises the possibility of waterborne illnesses in this area and suggests possible faecal contamination. This study highlights the necessity of routine monitoring, better sanitation procedures, and efficient water management techniques for drinking water safety. Furthermore, identifying different microorganisms' points to persistent biological contamination that endangers public health.

Keywords: *Physicochemical, Microbiological, Contamination, Waterborne Diseases*

INTRODUCTION

Water is essential for sustaining life, yet only 2.6% of Earth's water is freshwater. Of this, 76.4% is locked in glaciers and polar ice caps, and much remains underground or as atmospheric moisture. Only about 0.3% is accessible as surface water in rivers and lakes. This limited availability highlights the urgent need for sustainable water management (Oliveira, 2017). A basic human right is the availability of clean drinking water; yet, consumers may experience health issues if the water is contaminated with opportunistic pathogenic environmental bacteria (WHO, 2004). They may get polluted with bacteria as a result of interactions between these exposed water sources and sewage effluents, animal waste, and agricultural runoff (Obi *et al.*, 2002; Sharma *et al.*, 2005). The rate at which water supplies are being misused and deteriorating is concerning. This reduction is caused in part by population expansion, industrialisation, and urbanisation. Numerous microorganisms are currently contaminating clean water sources. In these unfavourable circumstances, their inherent biological traits are changing (Singh *et al.*, 2010). Knowing the physicochemical characteristics of water is necessary to evaluate its quality and suitability for different applications. Both human activity and natural forces have an impact on these attributes. Such understanding is necessary for the efficient use and management of water resources

(Gorde & Jadhav, 2013). In Pithoragarh, Uttarakhand, traditional water sources like "naula" and "dhara" are still essential to the local population. Because of their ease of use and accessibility, these sources have been trusted for many generations. Concerns over the water's quality, however, have increased recently. Due to the presence of harmful bacteria, residents are now concerned about their health and safety (Johnston *et al.*, 2001).

Throughout the year, seasonal changes in physico-chemical parameters impact the quality of drinking water. Both human activity and natural processes are responsible for these changes. Water safety and usability may be greatly impacted by such variations major health risks associated with contaminated water at specific seasons. Consuming it can lead to gastrointestinal infections, typhoid, diarrhoea, and dysentery caused by different types of bacteria such as *E. coli*, *Salmonella*, *Shigella*, *etc* (Fazal-ur-Rehman, 2019). The World Health Organization estimates that 1.1 billion people globally drink contaminated water. 88% of all diarrheal illness cases worldwide are caused by unsafe water, inadequate sanitation, and poor hygiene (WHO, 2002). Ten to twenty million people die each year from waterborne illnesses, which also cause about 250 million infections (Zamxaka *et al.*, 2004). In many parts of the world, waterborne illnesses continue to be a serious health concern. Every year, they are to blame for about 4 billion instances of diarrhoea. These conditions comprised 5.7% of the world's disease burden in 2000. This demonstrates the continuous harm to public health caused by contaminated water and inadequate sanitation (WHO, 2002).

The aim of conducting a physico-chemical assessment of community water sources in the Himalayan region of Pithoragarh, Uttarakhand, India. The primary objective of the study is to analyze the water quality of the community water sources and analyzed the microbial examination revealed the presence of bacteria in several water sources, such as *E. coli*, *Salmonella*, *Shigella*, *Clostridium* & *Campylobacter*. This investigation holds significant importance in guiding public health interventions and policy decisions related to water quality management, helping to prevent and control waterborne diseases and promoting safe drinking water access for the local community.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection: Water samples were taken from traditional drinking water sources at ten distinct study locations close to Pithoragarh City, which is situated in the northern Indian state of Uttarakhand at 29.5829° N, 80.2182° E. Shive Dhara (SD), Hanuman Mandir Dhara (HD), Rai Dhara (RD), Linthura Dhara (LD), Bin Naula (BN), Chungi Dhara (CD), Kumor Naula (KN), Ancholi Dhara (AD), Pavdeev Dhara (PD), and Mahadev Dhara (MD) are the locations for these studies (Photograph 1). Several sterile conical flasks covered with aluminium foil were filled with the samples. The neck was then filled around 30 cm below the water's surface after the cap cover was gently replaced. The sample location name, date, and time were then written on each bottle. The samples were promptly taken to the laboratory for bacteriological investigation after being stored in an icebox. All water sampling was done according to APHA (2012).

Physico-chemical analysis: Several crucial parameters, including hydrogen ion concentration (pH), water temperature (WT), atmospheric temperature (AT), total dissolved solids (TDS), dissolved oxygen (DO), carbon dioxide (CO₂), total alkalinity (TA), biological oxygen demand (BOD), and electric conductivity (EC), were used to evaluate the water quality after the sample was aseptically collected in 1000 ml sterile bottles with the method of APHA, 2012.

Microbial analysis: The components of selective media help target organisms flourish while preventing undesirable microorganisms from growing. The various bacteria have their own set of selective media produced. Xylose lysin deoxycholate agar media for *Shigella* (Gaurav *et al.*, 2013), lactose gelatin media for *Clostridium* (Lin & Labbe, 2003), skirrow's campylobacter media for *Campylobacter* (Bi *et al.*, 2013), 1 brilliant green agar media for *Salmonella* (Murchie *et al.*, 2008), eosin methylene blue agar media for *Escherichia coli* (Leininger *et al.*, 2001), and cefsulodin irgasan novobiocin media for *Yersinia* (Schiemann, 1979) were used. After that observed the bacterial characteristics morphology such as color,

Microbial contamination was examined at ten selected drinking water sources using various selective agar media to detect specific pathogenic bacteria. The study consistently identified *E. coli*, *Salmonella*, *Shigella*, *Campylobacter*, and *Clostridium* across all seasons, indicating continuous contamination. A significant rise in bacterial colonies was observed during the summer, which enhances microbial growth. Conversely, the lowest contamination levels were recorded during winter, suggesting seasonal variation in bacterial activity. Notably, *Yersinia* was completely absent from all sampling sites throughout the study, indicated in Table 3-8.

The bacterial culture characteristics of *E. coli*, *Shigella*, *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, and *Clostridium* showed distinct morphological patterns across months and locations. *E. coli* colonies were mostly white, round, and smooth, but some showed a metallic sheen or rough texture in certain months (Table 9). *Shigella* formed primarily yellow colonies with irregular shapes, though round forms also appeared; surfaces remained smooth (Table 10). *Salmonella* colonies were consistently pink, round, and smooth, indicating stable growth across all months (Table 11). *Campylobacter* colonies were usually white, occasionally turning grey, and maintained a round shape with smooth surfaces (Table 12). Color shifts in *Campylobacter* likely reflected metabolic changes. *Clostridium* colonies were mainly white but sometimes turned yellow, possibly due to metabolic variation (Table 13). These colonies were round and smooth regardless of color changes. Overall, each bacterium exhibited characteristic colony color, shape, and surface, as shown in Figure 1.

DISCUSSION

Our analysis of the physico-chemical parameters of various drinking water sources in this study is consistent with the findings of Patil (2010), Jasmin and Mallikarjuna (2014), and Qureshi *et al.*, (2021), who investigated the physico-chemical characteristics of groundwater quality parameters. The current study found that the water's temperature fluctuates with the seasons, which is consistent with the results of studies by Menberg *et al.*, (2014) and Gunawardhana and Kazama (2011) that examined the effects of climate change on groundwater temperature. In the present study, we analyzed the physicochemical properties of groundwater, which were similar to Robinson *et al.*, (1998) and Jasechko *et al.*, (2014), which worked on the seasonal differences in the groundwater recharge ratio, defined here as the ratio of groundwater recharge to precipitation.

In our study findings, the site-wise ANOVA analysis of various parameters revealed that p-values less than 0.05 for all parameters under investigation indicated statistical significance. This was comparable to the study conducted by Shenai-Tirodkar *et al.*, (2016), which focused on the assessment of water and sediment quality and discovered significant seasonal and site-wise variations of physicochemical parameters ($P < 0.05$). In our study, Tyagi *et al.*, (2015) investigated site-wise variation under ANOVA analysis between the major physicochemical characteristics. They looked at variations in drinking water sources across time and space. Using analysis of variance (ANOVA) to interpret their results, Jha *et al.*, (2013) and Bhardwaj *et al.*, (2018) carried out a thorough comparative examination of water quality metrics across various research locations.

According to Dinakaran *et al.*, (2023) findings, we also examined the presence of several bacteria in various water samples in our study by looking at the colonies across a variety of selective media. Zhang *et al.*, (2019) also observed the *E. coli* colonies on EMB agar displaying a metallic sheen color. In line with McConn *et al.*, (2024), *Salmonella* colonies were isolated on brilliant green agar, demonstrating the efficacy of the medium. According to Bolton & Robertson (1982), *Campylobacter* was effectively isolated using Skirrow's medium. The appearance of *Clostridium* colonies on selected gelatin agar was consistent with Wohlsen *et al.*, (2006) observations. In contrast to Cheyne *et al.*, (2009), we did not discover *Yersinia* while using CIN media, indicating environmental heterogeneity.

In this study, we observed the different morphology characteristics of different bacteria such as color, shape, and surface, which were similar to the observation of Singh & Sao (2015), and Batra (2018). We observed distinct culture characteristics of various bacterial species on selective media, which aligned

with the findings of Paul *et al.*, (2010); Kannahi & Sivasankari (2014) whose work focused on isolating and characterizing bacteria from selected areas, and reported similar observations to our study. In our study, we observed the cultured morphology of bacteria, which was similar to the findings of Chigbu & Sobolev (2007); Chouhan (2015) and Kim *et al.*, (2019), who isolated the colony morphology from drinking water sources and identified their distinct colony morphologies, findings that align with our observations.

Figure 1: Showing the colony of different bacteria on selective agar media (a) *E. coli*, (b) *Shigella*, (c) *Salmonella*, (d) *Campylobacter*, (e) *Clostridium*, and (f) *Yersinia* (No growth)

Table 1: Annual variations of all physicochemical parameters in all spots

Name of sites	pH	WT (°C)	AT (°C)	TDS (mg/l)	DO (mg/l)	CO ₂ (mg/l)	Alkalinity (mg/l)	BOD (mg/l)	EC (µs/cm)
SD	6.6-7.7 7.10±0.39	10-20 15.16±3.12	12-20 16.75±2.56	232-489 389.41±65.67	5.9-7.5 6.35±0.48	0.7-2.5 1.55±0.49	98-187 134.08±30.844	1.3-2.7 2.1±0.36	423-759 605.08±129.06
HM	6.4-7.7 6.98±0.43	9-20 15.08±3.36	11-21 16.83±3.53	321-489 399.75±53.48	5.5-7.3 6.44±0.47	0.9-2.6 1.78±0.56	92-186 137.16±30.12	1.2-3 2.01±0.55	434-759 621.25±124.19
RD	6.4-7.6 7.11±0.39	9-19 17.33±3.07	12-21 17.33±3.08	294-480 403.25±56.44	5.2-7.2 6.25±0.51	0.5-2.3 1.44±0.59	76-201 139.41±40.53	1.5-3.1 2.14±0.40	338-765 593.16±146.88
LD	6-7.8 7.05±0.54	9-19 16±3.13	12-21 17.08±3.55	348-491 436.16±44.44	6-7.9 6.77±0.62	0.4-2.3 1.48±0.58	152-287 195.58±41.72	1.2-2.6 2.05±0.39	354-729 568.16±117.62
BN	6.3-7.9 7.1±0.52	10-21 15.75±3.67	12-20 16.83±2.94	328-480 417.41±35.68	6-7.9 6.55±0.55	0.6-2.6 1.45±0.62	107-199 162.75±30.98	1.6-2.5 2.15±0.31	358-779 604.25±150.55
CD	6.1-7.3 6.92±0.43	9-18 14.33±3.02	12-20 16.83±2.85	314-490 403.91±46.52	5.9-7.2 6.47±0.42	0.8-2.2 1.61±0.49	59-198 127±43.38	1.7-2.7 2.10±0.31	308-799 595.41±142.07
KN	6.4-7.8 7.10±0.51	10-21 16±3.43	10-21 16.41±3.75	344-498 413.74±47.62	5.7-7.1 6.35±0.37	0.8-2.3 1.42±0.51	102-207 145.5±39.75	1.3-2.9 2.13±0.40	338-751 587.41±143.53
AD	6.1-7.9 7.07±0.49	7-19 14.58±3.50	10-22 17±3.64	300-490 377.91±66.31	5.8-7.1 6.45±0.38	0.6-2.4 1.61±0.62	117-189 153.08±24.94	1.4-2.4 2.05±0.32	341-737 558.33±142.81
MD	6.2-7.4 6.94±0.45	9-19 14.66±3.36	10-20 16.66±3.20	304-460 382.16±52.16	6-7.4 6.42±0.44	0.5-2.3 1.48±0.65	106-220 162.166±37.59	0.8-2.7 1.89±0.52	329-740 580.25±149.80
PD	6-7.6 7±0.56	10-20 15.91±3.34	12-22 18.33±3.70	342-473 402.08±45.75	6-7.9 6.67±0.58	1-2 1.61±0.33	102-188 142.33±28.46	1.2-2.8 1.95±0.47	418-748 580.91±124.87

Table 2: Site-wise analysis of variance test between different parameters

S. No.	Variation between different parameters	BG WG T	Sum of Squares (SS)	df	Mean Square (MS)	F	P value	Sig.
1	WT/ AT	BG	11.628125	1	11.628125	21.3899747	0.0002104	***
		WG	9.78525	18	0.543625			
		T	21.413375	19				
2	WT/ pH	BG	356.421245	1	356.421245	874.699869	1.03123E-16	***
		WG	7.33461	18	0.407478333			
		T	363.755855	19				
3	WT/ TDS	BG	749224.308	1	749224.308	5015.46613	1.77674E-23	***
		WG	2688.89016	18	149.3827867			
		T	751913.1982	19				
4	WT/ CO ₂	BG	971.199845	1	971.199845	2362.24712	1.50526E-20	***
		WG	7.40041	18	0.411133889			
		T	978.600255	19				
5	WT/DO	BG	405.72032	1	405.72032	972.981518	4.02455E-17	***
		WG	7.50576	18	0.416986667			
		T	413.22608	19				
6	WT/ BOD	BG	900.884645	1	900.884645	2204.86519	2.78675E-20	***
		WG	7.35461	18	0.408589444			
		T	908.239255	19				
7	WT/Alkalinity	BG	90351.20968	1	90351.20968	458.980511	2.92905E-14	***
		WG	3543.335142	18	196.8519524			
		T	93894.54482	19				
8	WT/EC	BG	1647041.357	1	1647041.357	9518.65369	5.64329E-26	***
		WG	3114.59429	18	173.0330161			
		T	1650155.952	19				

Table 3: *E. coli* colonies on selective agar media

S. no.	Sampling sites	Name of the months											
		Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
1.	SD	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
2.	HM	-	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	-
3.	RD	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
4.	LD	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
5.	CD	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
6.	BN	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+
7.	KN	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+
8.	AD	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
9.	MD	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+
10.	PD	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

(+) = Presence, (-) = Absence

Table 4: *Shigella* colonies on selective agar media

S.no.	Sampling sites	Name of the months											
		Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
1.	SD	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
2.	HM	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	-	-
3.	RD	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	+
4.	LD	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
5.	CD	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
6.	BN	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
7.	KN	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
8.	AD	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	-
9.	MD	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
10.	PD	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	-	+

(+) = Presence, (-) = Absence

Table 5: *Salmonella* colonies on selective agar media

S.no.	Sampling sites	Name of the months											
		Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
1.	SD	+	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-
2.	HM	-	+	-	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	+
3.	RD	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
4.	LD	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	-
5.	CD	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-
6.	BN	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
7.	KN	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
8.	AD	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
9.	MD	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+
10.	PD	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	-

(+) = Presence, (-) = Absence

Table 6: *Campylobacter* colonies on selective agar media

S.no.	Sampling sites	Name of the months											
		Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
1.	SD	+	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-
2.	HM	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	-
3.	RD	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
4.	LD	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	-
5.	CD	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	+
6.	BN	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
7.	KN	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
8.	AD	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
9.	MD	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	+
10.	PD	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	+

(+) = Presence, (-) = Absence

Table 7: *Clostridium* colonies on selective agar media

S.no.	Sampling sites	Name of the months											
		Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
1.	SD	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
2.	HM	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	-
3.	RD	+	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-
4.	LD	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
5.	CD	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	+
6.	BN	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
7.	KN	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
8.	AD	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	-
9.	MD	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	+
10.	PD	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+

(+) = Presence, (-) = Absence

Table 8: *Yersinia* colonies on selective agar media

S.no.	Sampling sites	Name of the months											
		Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
1.	SD	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	HM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3.	RD	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4.	LD	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5.	CD	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6.	BN	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7.	KN	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
8.	AD	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
9.	MD	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
10.	PD	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

(+) = Presence, (-) = Absence

Table 9: Cultural characteristics of *E. coli* growth on selective agar medium in the first year

S.no	Sites	Bacterial characterization												
		Morpho-logy	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
1.	SD	Color	White	Metallic	White	White	White	White	White	White	Metallic	White	-	White
		Shape	Round	Circular	Round	Round	Round	Circular	Round	Circular	Round	Circular	-	Circular
		Surface	Smooth	Rough	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Rough	Smooth	-	Smooth
2.	HM	Color	-	White	-	-	White	White	White	White	-	White	-	-
		Shape	-	Round	-	-	Circular	Round	Circular	Round	-	Round	-	-
		Surface	-	Smooth	-	-	Smooth	Smooth	Rough	Smooth	-	Smooth	-	-
3.	RD	Color	Metallic	-	White	White	White	White	Metallic	Metallic	Metallic	White	White	White
		Shape	Round	-	Round	Round	Round	Circular	Round	Circular	Round	Round	Round	Round
		Surface	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Rough	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth
4.	LD	Color	-	White	White	Metallic	White	White	White	White	White	White	White	White
		Shape	-	Circular	Round	Round	Round	Circular	Round	Circular	Round	Circular	Round	Circular
		Surface	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth								
5.	CD	Color	White	-	-	White	-	White						
		Shape	Round	-	-	Round	-	Round						
		Surface	Smooth	-	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Rough	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth
6.	BN	Color	White	-	White	White								
		Shape	Round	-	Round	Round								
		Surface	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Rough	Smooth	Smooth	-	Rough	Smooth
7.	KN	Color	White	Metallic	White	White	White	White	White	White	-	White	White	White
		Shape	Round	Circular	Round	Round	Round	Circular	Round	Round	-	Round	Round	Circular
		Surface	Smooth	Rough	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Rough	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth
8.	AD	Color	-	Metallic	White	White	White	White	Metallic	White	White	White	-	White
		Shape	-	Round	Circular	-	Circular							
		Surface	-	Rough	Smooth	Rough	-	Smooth						
9.	MD	Color	White	-	White	White	White	White	White	White	-	White	White	Metallic
		Shape	Round	-	Circular	Circular	Round	Circular	Round	Circular	-	Circular	Round	Circular
		Surface	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth
10.	PD	Color	White	metallic	-	White	White	White						
		Shape	Round	Round	-	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	Circular	Round	Round	Circular
		Surface	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth						

Table 10: Cultural characteristics of *Shigella* growth on selective agar medium in the first year

S. no	Site	Bacterial characterization												
		Morphology	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
1.	SD	Color	Yellow	-	-	Yellow	-							
		Shape	Irregular	-	-	Round	Irregular	-						
		Surface	Smooth	-	-	Smooth	-							
2.	HM	Color	Yellow	-	Yellow	Yellow	-	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	-	Yellow	-	-
		Shape	Irregular	-	Irregular	Irregular	-	Irregular	Irregular	Irregular	-	Irregular	-	-
		Surface	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	-	-
3.	RD	Color	-	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	-	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	-	Yellow
		Shape	-	Irregular	Irregular	Irregular	Irregular	Irregular	-	Irregular	Round	Irregular	-	Round
		Surface	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth
4.	LD	Color	Yellow	-	Yellow									
		Shape	Round	Round	Irregular	-	Round							
		Surface	Smooth	-	Smooth									
5.	CD	Color	-	-	-	Yellow	-	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	-
		Shape	-	-	-	Irregular	-	Irregular	Irregular	Irregular	Irregular	Irregular	Irregular	-
		Surface	-	-	-	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-
6.	BN	Color	Yellow											
		Shape	Round	Irregular	Round	Round								
		Surface	Smooth	Irregular	Smooth	Irregular	Smooth	Smooth						
7.	KN	Color	Yellow											
		Shape	Round	Irregular										
		Surface	Smooth	Irregular	Smooth									
8.	AD	Color	Yellow	-	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	-	Yellow	Yellow	-	-
		Shape	Irregular	-	Irregular	Irregular	Irregular	Irregular	Irregular	-	Round	Irregular	-	-
		Surface	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	-	-
9.	MD	Color	-	-	Yellow									
		Shape	-	-	Irregular	Round	Irregular							
		Surface	-	-	Smooth									
10.	PD	Color	Yellow	-	Yellow	Yellow	-	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	-	Yellow	-	Yellow
		Shape	Irregular	-	Irregular	Irregular	-	Irregular	Irregular	Irregular	-	Irregular	-	Irregular
		Surface	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	-	Smooth

Table 11: Cultural characteristics of *Salmonella* growth on selective agar medium in the first year

S.no	Sites	Bacterial characterization												
		Morpho-logy	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
1.	SD	Color	Pink	-	Pink	-	Pink	Pink	Pink	Pink	Pink	-	Pink	-
		Shape	Round	-	Round	-	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	-	Round	-
		Surface	Smooth	-	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	-
2.	HM	Color	-	Pink	-	Pink	-	-	Pink	-	Pink	Pink	-	Pink
		Shape	-	Round	-	Round	-	-	Round	-	Round	Round	-	Round
		Surface	-	Smooth	-	Smooth	-	-	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth
3.	RD	Color	Pink	Pink	Pink	-	Pink	Pink	Pink	Pink	Pink	Pink	Pink	-
		Shape	Round	Round	Round	-	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	-
		Surface	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-
4.	LD	Color	Pink	-	Pink	Pink	Pink	Pink	Pink	-	-	Pink	-	-
		Shape	Round	-	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	-	-	Round	-	-
		Surface	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	-	Smooth	-	-
5.	CD	Color	Pink	Pink	-	-	Pink	-	-	Pink	Pink	-	-	-
		Shape	Round	Round	-	-	Round	-	-	Round	Round	-	-	-
		Surface	Smooth	Smooth	-	-	Smooth	-	-	Smooth	Smooth	-	-	-
6.	BN	Color	Pink	Pink	Pink	Pink								
		Shape	Round	Round	Round	Round								
		Surface	Smooth	irregula r	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth							
7.	KN	Color	Pink	Pink	-	Pink								
		Shape	Round	Round	-	Round								
		Surface	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth								
8.	AD	Color	-	Pink	Pink	Pink	-	Pink	Purple	Pink	Pink	Pink	-	Pink
		Shape	-	Round	Round	Round	-	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	-	Round
		Surface	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth
9.	MD	Color	Pink	Pink	-	Pink	Pink	Pink	Pink	Pink	-	Pink	Pink	Pink
		Shape	Round	Round	-	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	-	Round	Round	Round
		Surface	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth
10.	PD	Color	-	Pink	Pink	Pink	-	Pink	Pink	Pink	Pink	-	Pink	-
		Shape	-	Round	Round	Round	-	Round	Round	Round	Round	-	Round	-
		Surface	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	-

Table 12: Cultural characteristics of *Campylobacter* growth on selective agar medium in the first year

S.no	Sites	Bacterial characterization													
		Morpho-logy	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	
1.	SD	Colour	White	-	Grey	-	Grey	White	Grey	White	Cream	-	-	-	
		Shape	Round	-	Round	-	Round	Circular	Circular	Circular	Circular	-	-	-	
		Surface	Smooth	-	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	-	-	
2.	HM	Colour	-	Cream	-	White	Grey	White	Grey	-	-	White	Grey	-	
		Shape	-	Circular	-	Circular	Circular	Circular	Circular	-	-	Circular	Round	-	
		Surface	-	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	-	Smooth	Smooth	-	
3.	RD	Colour	White	White	Cream	Grey	White								
		Shape	Circular												
		Surface	Smooth												
4.	LD	Colour	White	-	-	White	-	White	White	Grey	White	-	White	-	
		Shape	Round	-	-	Circular	-	Circular	Circular	Circular	Circular	-	Circular	-	
		Surface	Smooth	-	-	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	-	
5.	CD	Colour	-	Cream	-	White	White	White	White	-	White	-	White	White	
		Shape	-	Circular	-	Circular	Circular	Circular	Circular	-	Circular	-	Circular	Circular	
		Surface	-	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	
6.	BN	Colour	White												
		Shape	Circular	Round	Circular	Round	Circular								
		Surface	Smooth												
7.	KN	Colour	White	-	White	White	White	Cream							
		Shape	Circular	-	Circular	Circular	Round	Circular							
		Surface	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth							
8.	AD	Colour	White	-	-	White	-	White	White	White	Cream	White	-	-	
		Shape	Circular	-	-	Circular	-	Circular	Circular	Circular	Circular	Circular	-	-	
		Surface	Smooth	-	-	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	-	
9.	MD	Colour	-	White	-	White	White	White	White	White	-	White	-	White	
		Shape	-	Circular	-	Circular	Circular	Circular	Round	Circular	-	Circular	-	Circular	
		Surface	-	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	-	Smooth	
10.	PD	Colour	White	-	White	White	White	White	White	White	-	White	-	White	
		Shape	Circular	-	Circular	Circular	Circular	Circular	Circular	Circular	-	Circular	-	Circular	
		Surface	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	-	Smooth	

Table 13: Cultural characteristics of *Clostridium* growth on selective agar medium in the first year

S.no	Sites	Bacterial characterization													
		Morphology	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	
1.	SD	Color	White	-	White	Yellow	White	White	White	White	White	Yellow	White	-	White
		Shape	Round	-	Round	-	Circular								
		Surface	Smooth	-	Smooth	-	Smooth								
2.	HM	Color	-	White	-	White	White	White	White	White	Yellow	-	White	-	-
		Shape	-	Round	-	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	-	Round	-	-
		Surface	-	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	-	-
3.	RD	Color	White	-	White	-	White	White	White	White	White	White	-	White	Yellow
		Shape	Round	-	Round	-	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	-	Round	Round
		Surface	Smooth	-	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth
4.	LD	Color	White	White	White	Yellow	White	White	White	White	Yellow	White	White	White	
		Shape	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	
		Surface	Smooth	Irregular	Smooth										
5.	CD	Color	-	White	-	Yellow	White	White	-	White	-	White	-	White	
		Shape	-	Round	-	Round	Round	Round	-	Round	-	Round	-	Round	
		Surface	-	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	-	Smooth	-	Smooth	
6.	BN	Color	White	-	White	Yellow	White	Yellow	White						
		Shape	Round	-	Round										
		Surface	Smooth	-	Smooth										
7.	KN	Colour	White	White	Yellow	White	-	White							
		Shape	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	-	Round
		Surface	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth
8.	AD	Colour	White	-	-	White	White	White	White	White	-	White	White	-	
		Shape	Round	-	-	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	-	Round	Round	-	
		Surface	Smooth	-	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	-	
9.	MD	Colour	White	White	White	White	White	White	White	White	-	-	-	White	
		Shape	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	-	-	-	Round	
		Surface	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	-	-	Smooth	
10.	PD	Colour	-	White	-	White	White	White	-	White	White	White	White	White	
		Shape	-	Round	-	Round	Round	Round	-	Round	Round	Round	Round	Round	
		Surface	-	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	-	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	

CONCLUSION

The physico-chemical assessment of community water sources in the Himalayan region of Pithoragarh, Uttarakhand, has provided crucial insights into the overall quality and safety of drinking water in this remote and ecologically sensitive area. The study revealed seasonal variations in different parameters reflecting both natural environmental changes and human influences. The fluctuations indicate vulnerability to contamination and quality degradation. These findings highlight the urgent need for continuous monitoring of water quality and the implementation of protective measures to safeguard community health. Local authorities should prioritize the development of low-cost water purification solutions and ensure regular testing of water sources, especially during periods of increased contamination risk. Community engagement and education on safe water handling, sanitation, and hygiene practices are essential to mitigate the spread of waterborne diseases. Furthermore, improved infrastructure for waste management and sustainable water resource planning is critical in maintaining water safety over time. This study serves as a valuable resource for researchers and public health officials aiming to enhance water security in rural Himalayan regions and protect vulnerable populations from preventable health risks.

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